

Research IT Tenets

Committed focus on research and researchers

Move Research Forward	Champion Researchers	Partner	Solve Problems	Act with the Principles of Community at our core
<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>Research IT Services, first and foremost enables research and moves it forward.</p>	<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>Research IT puts research ahead of the process by understanding and supporting faculty activities and research requirements.</p>	<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>Research IT works to break down silos and partners with other RCD units and practitioners.</p>	<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>Research IT focuses on the work and not the silos, technology d'jour, or the latest service-provider.</p>	<p>What does this mean?</p> <p>Research IT does its part to maintain a climate of fairness, cooperation, and professionalism.</p>
<p>How do we do this? (The principle behind the tenet)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We recognize research needs and balance other mitigating factors 2. We take solutions-based actions 3. We prioritize research ahead of a given service or requirement. 	<p>How do we do this? (The principle behind the tenet)</p> <p>We don't forget that we are moving research forward and aiding better and faster time-to-research</p>	<p>How do we do this? (The principle behind the tenet)</p> <p>There is "enough research to go around" and support for research is welcome by other RCD practitioners supporting UC San Diego researchers.</p>	<p>How do we do this? (The principle behind the tenet)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We do our research to know the technologies, their applications, and the users. 2. We stay current to the best of our abilities 3. We identify and fill gaps. 	<p>How do we do this? (The principle behind the tenet)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We honor equity above equality 2. We lift up diversity <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. diversity of thought b. diversity of research disciplines c. diversity of people
<p>Specific actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We do not "sell" (or promote) a single service but provide clear options and make recommendations to the best of our (collective) abilities. 2. We creatively provide solutions. 3. We recognize how the research process has specific requirements - to that end, we identify and remove barriers that lead to decreased quality of support. 	<p>Specific actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Educating non-research experienced people on enterprise versus research differences 2. We listen to researchers with understanding of the research lifecycle, the challenges they face with grant cycles and requirements, tenure and promotion pressures, and teaching responsibilities 	<p>Specific actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Call upon our RCD support partners to join us in solving technology challenges faced by researchers. 2. Include our partners in consultations with researchers for efficient and effective use of time spent solving technology challenges. 	<p>Specific actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consider potential pitfalls in formulating solutions or recommendations 2. Implement solutions to get beyond roadblocks. 3. We assemble a suite of solutions for efficient workflows. 	<p>Specific actions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We are inclusive and mindful of diversity when setting agendas, inviting participants, creating programs, and more 2. We look beyond the established, well-funded researchers and remember to look to the long tail research with intentionality.